

Newly profiled uncharacterized bacterial species are responsible for most diet-induced microbiome changes in mouse models

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Supplementary figures

Supplementary Figure 6.1: Beta-diversity ordination plots. Ordination plots representing the first 2 principal components of a Multi Dimensional Scaling (MDS) performed on Braycurtis pairwise dissimilarity matrices computed on arcsine-square-rooted Species-level Genome Bins (SGBs) relative abundances from MetaPhlan 4 of a set of 9 mouse. In plots on the top, light blue indicates low-fat diet samples, dark yellow indicates high-fat diet samples. Left-side plot dot-sizes indicate percentage of fat in the mouse diet (before sampling); right-side plot-sizes indicate duration of the last diet administration. Bottom-plot dots are coloured by study-name.

Supplementary Figure 6.2: Prediction performance using gut samples from 7 mouse microbiome datasets. Cross-prediction matrices for the prediction of a high-fat vs. a low-fat diet feeding a Random Forest algorithm on arcsine-square-rooted microbial abundances computed via MetaPhlAn 4. Slots in the matrices represent AUCs of an algorithm trained on the corresponding row-dataset and tested on the corresponding column-dataset. Diagonal values are 10-fold cross-validations. LODO stands for Leave-One-Dataset-Out. Only datasets > 20 mice and datasets with only baseline samples and both high-fat and low-fat groups are retained. The left-side and the right-side matrices are from the MetaPhlAn 3, and the MetaPhlAn 4beta-profiled-data, respectively.

Supplementary Figure 6.3: metadata intrinsic correlations & agreement between fat-intake and diet-duration partial correlation analyses. a) regression plots of the centered duration of the administration of the diets (x-axis) and the centered fat-percentage (y-axis). Samples are coloured depending on the high- or low-fat-classification of the diet. Y-axis has been log-scaled in the high-fat group. **b)** 30 SGBs showing the highest correlation with dietary fat-intake in a meta-analysis of Spearman's correlation coefficients partialized by by age of the mouse, antibiotic usage (encoded as 1.0/0.0 variable), sampling body-site, genetic background and duration of the diet administration, an average prevalence > 20%, and a minimum presence in 4 datasets. Markers identify the single datasets, the black diamond indicates the random effect coefficient. White symbols refer to FDR>0.2, dark-yellow and light-blue symbols refer to a high-fat-related SGB and a low-fat-related one, respectively, both with a FDR<0.2. SGB abundances have been arcsin-square-rooted before the partial correlation. **c)** Agreement between the high-fat vs. low-fat meta-analysis and the fat-intake-correlation meta-analysis. Only random-effect coefficients from both analyses computed from SGBs present in a minimum of 4 studies are reported. **d)** agreement between a partial correlation analysis of SGB arcsine-square-rooted abundances and fat-percentage in the diet (Spearman's rho, corrected by antibiotics usage, days of administration and dataset, x-axis), and a partial correlation analysis of SGB arcsine-square-rooted abundance and duration of the administration of the diet (Spearman's rho, corrected by antibiotics usage, fat-intake and dataset, y-axis).